

Documentation on the aerosol bug in ICON scenario simulations provided for CORDEX-CMIP6

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This document gives a short description on an aerosol bug concerning regional climate scenario simulations run with ICON (*source_ids* [ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#) and [ICON-CLM-202407-1-3](#)), provided to [CORDEX-CMIP6](#) by the project “Updating the data basis for adaptation to climate change in Germany” (UDAG) and by the associated partners (*institution_ids* CLMcom-ETH and CLMcom-IMGW, forcing from NorESM2-MM). The evaluation and historical simulations are not affected. For the scenario simulations, the bug causes a mean offset of aerosol optical depth by 34 % (Fig. 1) with minor effects on surface downwelling shortwave radiation (relative bias of 2 %), near-surface temperature and wind, and negligible effects on other variables.

Fig. 1: (a) 2015–2100 mean difference of aerosol optical depth (*od550aer*) between the two MPI-ESM1-2-HR-driven scenario simulations with the bugfix (SSP126 1-2) and without the bugfix (SSP126 1-1); (b) area-averaged time series based on 5-year running averages of *od550aer* for the two scenarios, the respective historical simulation, and the other scenarios with MPI-ESM1-2-HR forcing.

The bug was identified when most of the affected simulations were already finished. As outlined below, the effects are minor apart from the obvious offset of aerosol optical depth. Therefore, it was decided to publish the simulations unmodified and to provide one additional scenario run (MPI-ESM1-2-HR-driven SSP126) with a bug-fixed model version (*source_id* [ICON-CLM-202407-1-2](#)) for documentation purposes. This additional scenario can also be used in analyses with a focus on aerosols (note that only a reduced set of output variables is published). The CMCC-CM2-SR5-driven scenarios provided by CLMcom-WEGC and CLMcom-FZJ were also run with ICON-CLM-202407-1-2 and, therefore, provide correct aerosol optical

depth.

In this document, we provide a short comparison of the two MPI-ESM1-2-HR-driven SSP126 simulations, which are identical apart from the bugfix, and set mean errors in relation to internal model variability. Additionally, we compare the time series of these two simulations to other scenario simulations with the same GCM forcing (MPI-ESM1-2-HR). Scenarios run with ICON-CLM-202407-1-1 or ICON-CLM-202407-1-3 using the boundary conditions from CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3-Veg, MIROC6, and NorESM2-MM are concerned as well, but it was considered sufficient to show the effects exemplarily for one GCM. See the list in the appendix for an overview of all scenario simulations run with ICON-CLM-202407-1-x.

Technical details on the aerosol bug

The aerosol bug was caused by an error in the implementation of the scaling factor, which can be applied on the externally provided cloud droplet number concentration (CDNC) climatology (namelist parameter *lscale_cdnc = .true.*). The scaling was only used for the scenario simulations. Thus, the evaluation and historical simulations of ICON-CLM-202407-1-1 and ICON-CLM-202407-1-2 are not concerned.

The CDNC scaling was introduced to account for the temporal change in line with the change of aerosol properties. Aerosol scenarios are provided by MACv2-SP (Stevens et al., 2017) used for the ICON simulations. The CDNC is used to model the indirect aerosol effect, i.e., aerosol-cloud-radiation interactions. The effects of the indirect aerosol effect itself are negligible over Europe in ICON (Geyer et al., 2026), but for physical consistency it was decided to consider it in the CORDEX-CMIP6 simulations, together with the CDNC scaling for the scenarios. For this scaling, the scaling factor of Stevens et al. (2017), Eq. 15, was used, but it had to be normalized with a reference year (which is a representative year of the externally prescribed CDNC climatology) as it was originally designed to derive the whole CDNC distribution from a prescribed background value and the current spatial distribution of aerosol optical depth. To retrieve the scaling factor from the simple plume scheme, it has to be called for this representative year (2005) and this erroneously also modified the aerosol optical depth itself. In consequence, the aerosol optical depth of the anthropogenic emissions of 2005 is added onto the current optical depth, causing an offset of *od550aer*, which is constant in time (Fig. 1b), with a weak annual cycle.

In ICON versions starting with [release icon-2025.10](#), the bug was fixed and the namelist parameter *scale_cdnc_mode = 1* replaces the setting *lscale_cdnc = .true.*

Note on intrinsic variability

The model intrinsic variability is estimated using the RMSE of the difference fields of two simulations in a similar setup, but for another time period (1979-1984) and with ERA5 forcing. The two simulations differ only by the initialization time (one was started one month earlier). See Geyer et al. (2026) for more details (specifically, Eq. 6).

Mean differences between the MPI-ESM1-2-HR-driven SSP126 simulations run with ICON-CLM-202407-1-1 and ICON-CLM-202407-1-2

The aerosol bug causes a mean offset in *od550aer* of 0.06, corresponding to a mean relative bias of 34 % with respect to the field average (Fig 1a). The bias is negative in Fig. 1 as the difference of the corrected simulation to the one with the bug is shown, i.e. the bug causes an unrealistically high *od550aer*. The offset is constant throughout all simulation years (Fig. 1b), with a weak annual cycle: it is maximum in May with 0.075 and minimum in November with 0.046. From a spatial perspective, the maximum (< 0.17) lies over eastern Europe, roughly the location of the plume for Europe from MACv2-SP.

Among the investigated variables, the largest impact of the increased *od550aer* is on *rsds* (Fig. 2). However, the mean bias of 2.3 W m^{-2} is very small (relative bias of 2 %); during model tuning (Geyer et al., 2026), *rsds* differences of up to $20\text{-}30 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ were not uncommon. Still, the RMSE of the difference field of the two

simulations for the first six simulation years (2015-2020) is higher than intrinsic variability (2.8 Wm^{-2} vs. 1.19 Wm^{-2} , Fig. 3).

Other variables with RMSE values above intrinsic variability are tas and sfcWind. The difference pattern depicted by od550aer and rsds also manifests itself in the tas and sfcWind difference fields (Fig. 2).

rsds mean bias IMS126L02 vs. IMS126L01 (2015-2100)
mean bias = 2.3063, rel. bias = 0.02, rmse = 2.7321

tas mean bias IMS126L02 vs. IMS126L01 (2015-2100)
mean bias = 0.0339, rel. bias = 0.00, rmse = 0.0652

clt mean bias IMS126L02 vs. IMS126L01 (2015-2100)
mean bias = 0.0608, rel. bias = 0.00, rmse = 0.1086

sfcWind mean bias IMS126L02 vs. IMS126L01 (2015-2100)
mean bias = 0.0094, rel. bias = 0.00, rmse = 0.0127

Fig. 2: (a) 2015-2100 mean difference between the two scenario simulations with (SSP126 1-2) and without the bugfix (SSP126 1-1) for surface downwelling shortwave radiation (rsds), near-surface (2 m) air temperature (tas), total cloud cover (clt), and near-surface (10 m) wind speed (sfcWind).

However, the mean biases are very small: for tas, the mean bias is 0.035 K with maximum values below 0.4 K; for sfcWind, the mean bias is below 0.01 m s^{-1} , with maxima below 0.08 m s^{-1} . For clt, the RMSE is as high as the intrinsic variability, but the spatial distribution seems more random compared to the other variables shown in Fig. 2.

The comparison with the other MPI-ESM1-2-HR driven ICON scenarios as given in the time series plots (Figs. 1a and 4) confirms the general results so far: For od550aer and for rsds, the difference between the SSP126 with and without bugfix is considerable, i.e. it is larger or as large as the spread generated by the

different scenarios. For the other variables shown (tas, clt, and sfcWind), it is minor to negligible for the domain average. More variables are given in the tables (Fig. 3), which were not analyzed in detail because the RMSEs are smaller than the intrinsic variability.

(a)	Season	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Year
Variable						
rsds [W m ⁻²]		0.678	1.405	1.325	0.985	1.192
clt [%]		0.526	0.633	0.575	0.382	0.263
sfcWind [m s ⁻¹]		0.034	0.048	0.036	0.027	0.019
tas [K]		0.081	0.063	0.054	0.046	0.031
tasmax [K]		0.166	0.073	0.083	0.060	0.132
tasmin [K]		0.218	0.076	0.056	0.056	0.127
pr [kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹]		0.127	0.107	0.123	0.085	0.058
psl [Pa]		9.963	7.642	5.259	6.406	4.761

(b)	Season	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Year
Variable						
rsds [W m ⁻²]		1.491	3.679	4.609	1.919	2.802
clt [%]		0.442	0.631	0.588	0.382	0.263
sfcWind [m s ⁻¹]		0.039	0.041	0.040	0.031	0.023
tas [K]		0.087	0.070	0.081	0.066	0.063
tasmax [K]		0.096	0.083	0.109	0.087	0.078
tasmin [K]		0.089	0.069	0.050	0.057	0.049
pr [kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹]		0.083	0.102	0.119	0.118	0.053
psl [Pa]		7.010	7.859	5.605	4.008	3.933

Fig. 3: (a) Intrinsic variability of ICON-CLM-202407-1-1 for selected variables, estimated for a 6-year period for the all-year temporal mean and the “climatological” seasons; (b) RMSEs of the two scenarios with and without bugfix for the first 6 simulation years (2015-2020).

Fig. 4: Domain-averaged time series based on 5-year running averages of rsds, tas, clt, and sfcWind for the historical simulation and all scenarios with MPI-ESM1-2-HR forcing for ICON-CLM-202407-1-1 (SSP126 1-1, SSP245, SSP370, SSP585) and for SSP126 for ICON-CLM-202407-1-2 (SSP126 1-2).

References

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Stevens, B., Fiedler, S., Kinne, S., Peters, K., Rast, S., Müsse, J., Smith, S. J., and Mauritsen, T.: MACv2-SP: a parameterization of anthropogenic aerosol optical properties and an associated Twomey effect for use in CMIP6, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 10, 433–452, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-433-2017>, 2017.

Appendix

List of scenario simulations run with ICON-CLM-202407-1-x providing data for the EUR-12 domain of CORDEX-CMIP6. Simulations run with **ICON-CLM-202407-1-2** are **with aerosol bugfix**:

[CLMcom-BTU/CNRM-ESM2-1/ssp126/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-BTU/CNRM-ESM2-1/ssp245/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-BTU/CNRM-ESM2-1/ssp370/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-BTU/CNRM-ESM2-1/ssp585/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-DWD/MPI-ESM1-2-HR/ssp126/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-DWD/MPI-ESM1-2-HR/ssp126/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-2](#)
[CLMcom-DWD/MPI-ESM1-2-HR/ssp245/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-DWD/MPI-ESM1-2-HR/ssp370/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-DWD/MPI-ESM1-2-HR/ssp585/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-GERICS/EC-Earth3-Veg/ssp126/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-GERICS/EC-Earth3-Veg/ssp370/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-Hereon/EC-Earth3-Veg/ssp245/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-Hereon/EC-Earth3-Veg/ssp585/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-KIT/MIROC6/ssp126/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-KIT/MIROC6/ssp245/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-KIT/MIROC6/ssp370/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-KIT/MIROC6/ssp585/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-1](#)
[CLMcom-FZJ/CMCC-CM2-SR5/ssp126/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-2](#)
[CLMcom-WEGC/CMCC-CM2-SR5/ssp370/r1i1p1f1/ICON-CLM-202407-1-2](#)
[CLMcom-IMGW/NorESM2-MM/ssp126/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-3](#)
[CLMcom-ETH/NorESM2-MM/ssp245/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-3](#)
[CLMcom-IMGW/NorESM2-MM/ssp370/r1i1p1f2/ICON-CLM-202407-1-3](#)